

PROJECT SCHEDULE MANAGEMENT ON PERFORMANCE OF CONSTRUCTION PROJECT IN NORTH RIFT REGION, KENYA

Martin Mengich^{1,1*}, Dr. Elizabeth Nambuswa Makokha^{1,2} (PhD)

¹. School of Business, Department of Economics, Accounting and Finance, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, P.O. Box 62000 - 00200, Nairobi Kenya

². School of Business, Department of Economics, Accounting and Finance, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, P.O. Box 62000 - 00200, Nairobi Kenya

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Abstract: The purpose of the study was to examine the effect of project schedule management on performance of construction projects in North Rift region, Kenya. The study was guided by the following specific objectives; as to determine the effect of project tasks definition on performance of construction projects in North Rift region, Kenya. The target population was 100 professionals comprising of general foremen of contractors registered by the National Construction Authority implementing construction projects in North Rift region Kenya for their mandate of project execution, encompassing construction schedule control. Data collection instrument was questionnaire. Piloting was done to test the validity and reliability of the data collection instrument. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The target population was 100 professionals comprising of general foremen of contractors registered by the National Construction Authority implementing construction projects in North Rift region Kenya for their mandate of project execution, encompassing construction schedule control. Due to the small size of the study populace, a census was used. Data collection instrument was questionnaire. Piloting was done for validity and reliability. The data was analyzed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 27. The study used Correlation and Regression analysis to estimate the causal relationships between variables. Multiple regression analysis and ANOVA was used to test the significance level of variables. Based on the findings, the study concluded that project task definition has significant effect on performance of construction projects in North Rift region, Kenya. The study came up with the following recommendations; The management should define project task since it is a critical step in project planning that involves identifying and clearly outlining all the specific actions or units of work necessary to complete a project successfully.

Keywords: project schedule management, construction projects, National Construction Authority.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years the interest in project management has significantly increased Project scheduling is a critical component of construction project management that directly influences the overall performance and success of a project (Papulova, E. 2020). It involves the detailed planning and allocation of time and resources to specific tasks and activities in order to ensure that a construction project is completed within the stipulated timeframe (Osman et al., 2022). A well-prepared schedule serves as a roadmap that guides project teams from inception through execution to completion (Parizotto, et al., (2020). It enables managers to visualize the sequence of operations, identify dependencies among tasks, and allocate resources more

efficiently (Chai, 2022; Aumayr, 2023). Proper scheduling ensures that construction activities are carried out in a logical and coordinated manner, thereby minimizing delays and disruptions (Titarenko et al., 2025). The performance of construction projects is often measured in terms of time, cost, quality, and scope (Pieterse et al., 2022). Effective project scheduling significantly enhances performance in these areas by promoting timely delivery of outputs, controlling project costs, and ensuring adherence to quality standards (Osman et al., 2022). When schedules are realistic and based on accurate information, they help prevent cost overruns and resource wastage, which are common challenges in the construction industry (Kaminsky, J. 2021). Moreover, a well-defined schedule allows for better risk management since it facilitates the identification of potential delays and the development of contingency plans to address them (Titarenko et al., 2025).

Another way in which project scheduling contributes to performance is through improved communication and coordination among stakeholders (Amer, 2020). Construction projects typically involve multiple teams, including architects, engineers, contractors, and suppliers. A clear schedule ensures that all parties are aligned in terms of expectations and deliverables (Chen et al., 2023). It fosters accountability by assigning specific tasks to individuals or groups within defined timeframes, thereby reducing confusion and conflicts. This alignment not only boosts productivity but also enhances stakeholder satisfaction (Titarenko et al., 2025). Additionally, project scheduling supports performance monitoring and evaluation. It provides a framework against which actual progress can be measured, allowing for timely adjustments when deviations occur (Amer, 2020). Project managers can use scheduling tools to track milestones, monitor task completion rates, and assess whether the project is on track (Abwunza, et al., 2020). This ongoing monitoring helps in maintaining project momentum and achieving the desired outcomes without compromising quality or incurring additional costs (Harvey & Aubry, 2018).

Regionally, project scheduling offers a specified plan that shows how and when the project will provide the services, products, and results stated in the project scope and includes the processes necessary to ensure the timely completion of the project (PMI, 2017). The result of effective schedule management leads to an increase in productivity and effectiveness (Nsirim, 2023; Okolocha et al., 2023). However, implementing good schedule control in practice is commonly considered to be a challenging task (Olawale, 2020). The efficiency of project management can be influenced by various causes, which can potentially lead to delays and cost deviations in the project (Ahabab et al., 2019). Schedule overruns are a reoccurring problem on large projects, despite evident progress of the project management profession (Simushi & Wium, 2020). The result of delays in the project negatively affects all project stakeholders (Oburu, 2020). Schedule management is seen as a vital part of management. It is viewed this way because time is a meager resource, that cannot be stored once incurred or utilized, which in turn means it is impossible to keep time and use it in the future, and if unused, it will be lost forever (Muli, Muchelule & Makokha 2025). Moreover, goals of management cannot be achieved without efforts that always consume time (Oburu, 2020). Schedule project control is important, because it serves as the means to prevent project failure (Olawale, 2020). Extending the expected schedule limits is a serious problem in project management. Stumpf (2000) defines schedule delay as an event or act that prolongs the time allocated to finish the task beyond the set contract deadline. The need to optimize projects made politicians, academics, and other parties acknowledge of the challenges demonstrated by the reoccurring time overruns (Ahabab et al., 2019). Delays in schedule were caused by uncertain activities during the project life cycle that have a possibility of putting the project at risk (Susanti, 2019). To this day the delay situation is unstructured and not defined coherently, therefore the studies related to delay and the necessary solutions to overcome it are still being conducted (Abwunza et al., 2020).

Basically, a global problem as most of the construction industry around the world, do exceeds the expected budget often. A global study by Memon, Rahman and Azis (2017) on construction projects has found that; cost overrun is the most faced problem, with an estimation of 9 out of 10 projects facing the problem with an overrun of 50% to 100%. Likewise, another investigation on 87 projects conducted by Naveenkumar and Prabhu (2016) revealed that; the problem of schedule overrun exists in projects by an average of 10.3%, giving an example of the United Kingdom (UK) where nearly one third of all clients' files complain about their projects exceeding their allocated budget. Malaysia is also another country being affected severely by cost overrun, in which only 46.8% of public sector and 37.2% of private sector projects are being finished within the allocated budget (Memon, 2016).

The Contractors registration establishment in Kenya has 8 distinct categories ranging from NCA1 (Highest) to NCA8 (Lowest) with most of the contractors doing more than one class of work (Kiungo & Otieno, 2023). The main classes of work include Roads, Water, Building, Electrical and Mechanical. There are a total of over 13,700 contractors registered by NCA with over 22,400 licenses in the above classes of work (Nabwile et al., 2025).

According to Ogotu and Muturi (2017), building works has the highest proportion of licensed contractors at 43% followed by Roads at 34%. Water and Electrical works have proportions of 10% and 9% respectively. Mechanical has a paltry 3%. The sector is dominated by small and medium enterprise contractors which account for a total of 79% with NCA5 11%, NCA6 22%, NCA7 31% and NCA8 15%. Large establishment contractors account for 21% with NCA4 13%, NCA3 4%, NCA2 2% and NCA1 3% (Nyangilo, 2016). There are over 169,000 semiskilled and 214,000 unskilled construction workers currently employed by contractors in the industry. There is need for specific training courses to improve skills and competencies of this category of workers in the industry (Nabwile et al., 2025). In addition, contractors should be sensitised to take training/upgrading of their employee's skills as a strategy for quality improvement, higher productivity and profitability (Phiri, 2016).

In Kenya, the construction industry contributes up to 5% of the National GDP as reported in the Economic Survey and contributes 10% to employment nationally (S Karuga · 2024). Its contribution is valued at 50% in terms of demand which is a significant proportion from a single Client (Nyangwara & Datche, 2016). The provision of infrastructure consumes about 10% of the National Budget as indicated in the Printed Estimates (Mose & Moronge, 2016). In Kenya, delays of building works projects are rampant especially due to endemic corruption and poor reporting structures among the public sector (Mbatha, 2017). According to Kogi and Were (2017), foreign investors have shown a lot of keenness to have a stake in Kenya considered a business hub in east and central Africa and a centre from which they can operate with in Africa. As a result of this, Marakwet and its environs has witnessed a boom in building works projects (Nabwile et al., 2025). These projects are government, private individuals, private companies and international businesses and institutions sanctioned (Kiungo & Otieno, 2023).

Building and construction is quite central to creating numerous employment opportunities which would help in reducing the unemployment levels which are a problem in many countries Kenya included (Kihoro, 2017). Many of the projects are labour intensive and thus very many of otherwise unemployed people of the working age are employed in this industry. In Kenya many government projects fail to be completed in time causing cost overruns and at times complete abandonment (Mose & Moronge, 2016). This can be seen in various number of building projects which stand unfinished. Even more are those projects that are in the end finished but at an inflated budget and at a date later than agreed in the project schedule (Kogi & Were, 2017). Mega construction projects are not just magnified versions of smaller projects but are a completely different breed of project in terms of their level of aspiration, lead times, complexity, and stakeholder involvement; implying that they are also a very different type of project to manage. Building works projects are also among the most complex category of project (Murithi, Makokha & Otieno, 2017). Inherent complexity in mega building works projects is the main source of contextual risk which is usually referred to as typological risk. The magnitude of this risk increases as we move from an environment of low complexity towards high complexity (Ogotu & Muturi, 2017). According to Mose and Moronge (2016), the effectiveness of project schedule control is usually affected by typological risk in such a way that as the value of the typological risk increases, exercising project control becomes more difficult. This could explain why complex building works megaprojects are usually delivered over budget, behind schedule, with benefit shortfalls, over and over again.

Despite the critical role of project scheduling in the successful execution of construction projects, many projects continue to suffer from delays, cost overruns, poor quality, and inefficient resource utilization. In both public and private construction sectors, failure to adhere to well-developed schedules has led to significant setbacks, including contractual disputes, financial losses, and unmet stakeholder expectations. The construction industry is inherently complex, involving numerous interdependent activities, multiple stakeholders, and dynamic site conditions. Without a structured and realistic schedule, it becomes challenging to coordinate these variables effectively, resulting in project underperformance. In many cases, inadequate scheduling practices stem from the use of outdated tools, lack of technical expertise, poor communication among stakeholders, and limited attention to risk factors during planning (S Karuga · 2024). Additionally, frequent changes in project scope, lack of timely approvals, and delays in material supply further undermine the effectiveness of initial schedules. As a result, projects are often completed later than planned, at higher costs, and with compromised quality, affecting the overall performance and sustainability of construction initiatives. Given the growing demand for infrastructure development and the increasing complexity of construction projects, it is imperative to understand how project scheduling practices influence project performance. However, there is limited empirical evidence, particularly in developing contexts, that clearly links project scheduling to key performance indicators such as time efficiency, cost control, and quality outcomes. The general objective of the study was to examine the effect of project schedule management on performance of

construction projects in North Rift region, Kenya. The study was guided by the following specific objective; To determine the effect of project tasks definition on performance of construction projects in North Rift region, Kenya.

2. PROJECT TASKS DEFINITION

Project task definition is a critical step in project planning that involves identifying and clearly outlining all the specific actions or units of work necessary to complete a project successfully. It serves as the foundation upon which the entire project structure is built, ensuring that each team member understands what needs to be done, how it fits into the overall project objectives, and who is responsible for each task (Titarenko et al., 2025). Defining tasks involves more than simply listing activities—it requires a detailed breakdown of the scope of work into manageable components, often using tools like a Work Breakdown Structure (WBS). Each task must be described in terms of its goals, expected outputs, required resources, duration, and dependencies on other tasks. This clarity helps avoid confusion, overlaps, and omissions, which can lead to delays or inefficiencies. Moreover, well-defined tasks facilitate better scheduling, budgeting, resource allocation, and risk identification. In large and complex projects, such as those in construction or infrastructure development, task definition is particularly important because it enables effective coordination among multiple teams, contractors, and stakeholders. Without properly defined tasks, a project is more likely to suffer from miscommunication, accountability issues, and scope creep. Therefore, task definition is not just an administrative exercise, but a strategic process that significantly enhances the likelihood of delivering a project on time, within budget, and to the desired quality standards (Titarenko et al., 2025).

The success of a project is largely dependent on the ability to define tasks and activities clearly and effectively. Whether you are working on a complex construction project, launching a new product, or organizing a large event, defining tasks and activities is the first step towards achieving your goals and realizing your vision (Acquah, Eyiah & Oteng, 2018). In project management, a task is a work item or activity with a specific purpose related to the larger goal. It's a necessary step on the road towards project completion. A task is a single unit of work — a single step in a multi-step project. A task is accomplished by a set deadline and must contribute towards work-related objectives. Just as project management is the coordination of individual tasks, a task can be further broken down into subtasks, which should also have clear start and end dates for completion. A task in project management is a specific piece of work that contributes to the overall success of the project. It is a unit of work that has a well-defined purpose, a specific outcome, and a deadline for completion. A task can range in size and complexity, and it can take anywhere from a few minutes to several months to complete.

Tasks are the building blocks of a project, and they are the key to achieving project success. A well-defined task has a clear objective, is measurable, and can be completed by a specific person or team. Effective project management involves breaking down the project into smaller, manageable tasks and then organizing and executing those tasks in a structured and efficient manner. Whether you are a seasoned project manager or just starting, understanding the importance of tasks in project management is the first step toward success. It is important in the management of processes in a project to clearly define roles and responsibilities in order to ensure that they are implemented successfully (Ananatmula, 2010). It leads to increase in responsibility of the team members towards their job since their roles have been clearly spelt out and their performance is measured against the same. Responsibility matrix is a popular tool which is used for the purpose of clarifying roles and responsibilities.

Performance of construction projects refers to the extent to which a construction project achieves its intended goals in terms of time, cost, quality, safety, and client satisfaction. It is a comprehensive evaluation of how effectively and efficiently a construction project is planned, managed, and executed. Given the complexity and scale of construction activities—which often involve multiple stakeholders, intricate designs, regulatory requirements, and dynamic environments—measuring performance is essential for ensuring project success and continuous improvement in the construction industry. One of the primary indicators of construction project performance is time management, which assesses whether the project is completed within the planned schedule. Delays can occur due to poor planning, inadequate resourcing, unforeseen site conditions, weather disruptions, or miscommunication among stakeholders. Effective scheduling, monitoring, and control mechanisms are critical to maintaining time performance and avoiding costly overruns. Another vital dimension is cost performance, which evaluates how well the project adheres to its allocated budget. Cost overruns are a common challenge in construction and can result from inaccurate estimates, material price fluctuations, changes in scope, or inefficient procurement. Maintaining cost performance requires rigorous budgeting, real-time financial tracking, and contingency planning.

Quality performance is also central to project success. It involves ensuring that construction works meet the required standards, specifications, and client expectations. Poor quality can lead to structural failures, costly rework, and long-term safety issues. Quality control mechanisms such as inspections, audits, and adherence to building codes help maintain high standards of construction. Safety performance is another critical aspect, especially considering the high-risk nature of construction sites. A successful project must ensure the health and safety of workers, minimize accidents, and comply with occupational health and safety regulations. Safety performance is often tracked through the number of incidents, near-misses, and implementation of safety protocols.

Challal and Tkiouat, (2016) opine that contractors should appoint project manager, who are expected to draw up a workable project plan, and strategies which should implement the project activities in the proper sequence, to complete the defined stages of the project within the stipulated time frame, with designated resources. Darusi and Makokha (2018) assert on improving the ability of managers and engineers which may mitigate schedule overrun as they reduce the human and management problems. Furthermore, Ghaffari and Emsley (2017) also insists on performing appropriate and proper preconstruction planning on tasks and resources, which may help on monitoring the project progress against stipulated time and budget. A faulty planning and scheduling may lead to project delays due to poor site management and supervision; hence leading to the misunderstanding between owner, consultant and building contractors. Hornstein (2017) suggested possible mitigation measures in dealing with delay and cost overrun in public building project such as; frequent progress management meeting; consistent supervision, site and technical meetings; frequent coordination between the parties involved; use of up-to-date technology and construction methods; clear information and communication channel among project team members; and delay in decision making. Clients are the project owner, when they do not make decisions on time regarding project matters, they slow down on-site project activities. This compliments Memon (2016) findings that; slow decision making could be caused by an organization's internal bureaucracy, or wrong channel of communication in building projects.

Construction scheduling is the process of developing, maintaining and communicating schedules for construction time, resources and tasks (Ray, 2017). A schedule is the timetable for a construction project. Schedules are presented in many different ways in order to suit the circumstances. The most common form of graphical schedule is the Gantt chart. On conclusion of the work, schedules that show what was planned and what actually happened are an important resource in determining lessons learned (Ecker, 2018). It is the desire of stakeholders that management practices don't procrastinate, but rather, expedite the accomplishment and delivery of the construction project within the scheduled time frame.

3. METHOD

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. Sekran (2007) observed that descriptive survey research is intended to produce statistical information about aspects of a phenomenal being studied by administering a questionnaire to a sample of individuals. The descriptive design was particularly ideal because all the data on the indicators of effect of project schedule management on performance of construction projects was in numerical form suitable for quantitative description. The qualitative data was analyzed quantitatively by use of five-point Likert scale items in the questionnaire. The target population was 100 professionals comprising of general foremen of contractors registered by the National Construction Authority implementing construction projects in North Rift region Kenya for their mandate of project execution, encompassing construction schedule control. Due to the small size of the study populace, a census was used. Data collection instrument was questionnaire. The study adopted a structured questionnaire. Structured questionnaires were prepared and pre-tested to include all quantitative data pertaining to the proposed study. The questionnaires had questions regarding variables of the study and the Likert scale will be used with respondents answering the questions in each variable based on a strength of 1 to 5 where 1 is "Strongly Disagree", 2 is "Disagree", 3 is "Neutral", 4 is "Agree", and 5 is "Strongly Agree". Questionnaires was issued to project professionals. This is carried out on the study as a critical pre-test for establishing the validity and the reliability of the instrument for the collection of data in order to improve and determine the validity and the reliability of the instruments (Gibson, 2017). Once data for this study was collected from the population, cleaned, organized to attach meaning, and tested for reliability and validity, then the analysis of the data was follow in order to enable the testing of the study and respond appropriately to the research objectives and questions by establishing meaning in the data collected. After data was collected and all the completed questionnaires re- turned, preliminary analytical steps of editing, coding and tabulation was done. These was to ensure that the data is accurate, reliable, compete and suitable for further detailed analysis (Sekaran and Bougie, 2010). This study used both descriptive and inferential statistics to analyse the data.

Descriptive statistics was to describe and summarize the data in a meaningful way. The coded data was entered into a computer and the SPSS (Statistical package for social sciences) version 27. Here percentages to depict population characteristics such as the legality of the enterprise were obtained. The mean and standard deviation, correlation and regression analysis was carried out in order to establish the contribution of each independent variable to the dependent variable. Correlation was used to measure the relationship between the variables' (independent and dependent variables). Regression was used to estimate the average relationship and predict the most likely values of one variable for specified values of the other variable.

4. DISCUSSIONS

The first specific objective of the study was to determine the effect of project tasks definition on performance of construction projects in North Rift region, Kenya. The respondents were requested to indicate their level of agreement on statements relating to the effect of project tasks definition on performance of construction projects in North Rift region, Kenya. A 5 point Likert scale was used where 1 symbolized strongly disagree, 2 symbolized disagree, 3 symbolized neutral, 4 symbolized agree and 5 symbolized strongly agree. The results were as presented in Table 4.1.

From the results, the respondents agreed that project task definition is a critical step in project planning that involves identifying and clearly outlining all the specific actions or units of work necessary to complete a project successfully. This is supported by a mean of 3.851 (std. dv = 0.961). In addition, as shown by a mean of 4.782 (std. dv = 0.895), the respondents agreed that It serves as the foundation upon which the entire project structure is built, ensuring that each team member understands what needs to be done, how it fits into the overall project objectives, and who is responsible for each task. The respondents agreed that defining tasks involves more than simply listing activities it requires a detailed breakdown of the scope of work into manageable components, often using tools like a Work Breakdown Structure (WBS). This is shown by a mean of 3.751 (std. dv = 0.983).

The respondents also agreed that Each task must be described in terms of its goals, expected outputs, required resources, duration, and dependencies on other tasks. This is shown by a mean of 3.906 (std. dv = 0.954). With a mean of 3.403 (std. dv = 0.873), the respondents agreed that This clarity helps avoid confusion, overlaps, and omissions, which can lead to delays or inefficiencies. Further, the respondents agreed that moreover, well-defined tasks facilitate better scheduling, budgeting, resource allocation, and risk identification as without properly defined tasks, a project is more likely to suffer from miscommunication, accountability issues, and scope creep. This is shown by a mean of 3.641 (std. dv = 0.976).

Table 4.1: Effect of project tasks definition on performance of construction projects in North Rift region, Kenya

	Mean	Std. Deviation
Project task definition is a critical step in project planning that involves identifying and clearly outlining all the specific actions or units of work necessary to complete a project successfully.	3.851	0.961
It serves as the foundation upon which the entire project structure is built, ensuring that each team member understands what needs to be done, how it fits into the overall project objectives, and who is responsible for each task	4.782	0.895
Defining tasks involves more than simply listing activities—it requires a detailed breakdown of the scope of work into manageable components, often using tools like a Work Breakdown Structure (WBS)	3.751	0.963
Each task must be described in terms of its goals, expected outputs, required resources, duration, and dependencies on other tasks	3.906	0.954
This clarity helps avoid confusion, overlaps, and omissions, which can lead to delays or inefficiencies	3.603	0.873
Moreover, well-defined tasks facilitate better scheduling, budgeting, resource allocation, and risk identification as without properly defined tasks, a project is more likely to suffer from miscommunication, accountability issues, and scope creep	3.641	0.976
Aggregate	3.902	0.895

4.1. Performance of construction projects in North Rift region, Kenya.

The respondents were requested to indicate their level of agreement on various statements relating to performance of construction projects in North Rift region, Kenya. A 5 point Likert scale was used where 1 symbolized strongly disagree, 2 symbolized disagree, 3 symbolized neutral, 4 symbolized agree and 5 symbolized strongly agree. The results were as presented in table 4.2.

From the results, the respondents agreed that the construction project achieves its intended goals in terms of time. This is supported by a mean of 4.281 (std. dv = 0.957). In addition, as shown by a mean of 3.978 (std. dv = 0.841), the respondents agreed that the construction project achieves its intended goals in terms cost. The responded also agreed that the construction project achieves its intended goals in terms quality. This is shown by a mean of 3.823 (std. dv = 0.752). The respondents in addition agreed that project scheduling enhances continuous improvement in the construction industry. This is shown by a mean of 3.812 (std. dv = 0.843). With a mean of 3.743 (std. dv = 0.925), the respondents agreed that the construction project achieves its intended goals in terms safety and client satisfaction. The respondent also agreed that project schedule management enhances performance of construction project in Kenya. This is shown by a mean of 3.961 (std. dv = 0.911).

Table 4.2: Performance of Construction Projects in North Rift region, Kenya.

	Mean	Std. Deviation
The construction project achieves its intended goals in terms of time	4.281	0.957
The construction project achieves its intended goals in terms cost	3.978	0.841
The construction project achieves its intended goals in terms quality	3.823	0.752
The construction project achieves its intended goals in terms safety and client satisfaction	3.812	0.843
Project scheduling enhances continuous improvement in the construction industry.	3.743	0.925
Project schedule management enhances performance of construction project in Kenya	3.961	0.911
Aggregate	3.817	0.818

4.2 Inferential Statistics

Inferential statistics in the current study focused on correlation and regression analysis. Correlation analysis was used to determine the strength of the relationship while regression analysis was used to determine the relationship between dependent variable (performance of construction projects in North Rift region, Kenya and the independent (project task definition).

4.2.1 Correlation Analysis

The present study used Pearson correlation analysis to determine the strength of association between independent variables (project task definition,) and the dependent variable (performance of construction projects in North Rift region, Kenya) dependent variable. Pearson correlation coefficient range between zero and one, where by the strength of association increase with increase in the value of the correlation coefficients. The current study employed Taylor (2018) correlation coefficient ratings where by 0.80 to 1.00 depicts a very strong relationship, 0.60 to 0.79 depicts strong, 0.40 to 0.59 depicts moderate, 0.20 to 0.39 depicts weak.

Table 4.3: Correlation Coefficients

	Performance of construction projects	Project task definition
Performance of construction projects	Pearson Correlation	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	
Project task definition,	N	85
	Pearson Correlation	.841**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001
	N	85

From the results, there was a very strong relationship between Project task definition and performance of construction projects in North Rift region, Kenya. ($r = 0.841$, p value = 0.001). The relationship was significant since the p value 0.001 was less than 0.05 (significant level).

4.2.2 Regression Analysis

Multivariate regression analysis was used to assess the relationship between independent variables (project task definition) and the dependent variable (performance of construction projects in North Rift region, Kenya).

Table 4.4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.801	.621	.611	.311121

a. Predictors: (Constant), project task definition,

The model summary was used to explain the variation in the dependent variable that could be explained by the independent variables. The r-squared for the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable was 0.621. This implied that 62.1% of the variation in the dependent variable (performance of construction projects in North Rift region, Kenya) could be explained by independent variables (project task definition).

Table 4.5: Analysis of Variance

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	29.011	1	3.015	62.03	.000 ^b
1 Residual	6.461	84	.033		
Total	35.472	85			

a. Dependent Variable: performance of construction projects in North Rift region, Kenya

b. Predictors: (Constant), project task definition,

The ANOVA was used to determine whether the model was a good fit for the data. F calculated was 62.03. The p value was 0.000. Since the F-calculated was greater than the F-critical and the p value 0.000 was less than 0.05, the model was considered as a good fit for the data. Therefore, the model can be used to predict the effect of project task definition on performance of construction projects in North Rift region, Kenya.

Table 4.6 Regression Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	0.502	0.034		5.902	0.000
	Project task definition	0.685	0.065	0.365	4.090	0.000

a Dependent Variable: Performance of construction projects in North Rift region, Kenya.

The regression model was as follows:

$$Y = 0.502 + 0.685X_1 + \epsilon$$

According to the results, project task definition has a significant effect on performance of construction projects in North Rift region, Kenya. ($\beta_1=0.685$, p value= 0.000). The relationship was considered significant since the p value 0.004 was less than the significant level of 0.05.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The first specific objective of the study was to determine the effect of project tasks definition on performance of construction projects in North Rift region, Kenya. The findings revealed that project task definition is a critical step in project planning that involves identifying and clearly outlining all the specific actions or units of work necessary to complete a project successfully and that It serves as the foundation upon which the entire project structure is built, ensuring that each team member understands what needs to be done, how it fits into the overall project objectives, and who is responsible for each task. The findings also implied that defining tasks involves more than simply listing activities it requires a detailed breakdown of the scope of work into manageable components, often using tools like a Work Breakdown Structure (WBS). Further the findings implied that each task must be described in terms of its goals, expected outputs, required resources,

duration, and dependencies on other tasks and that clarity helps avoid confusion, overlaps, and omissions, which can lead to delays or inefficiencies. The findings also implied that moreover, well-defined tasks facilitate better scheduling, budgeting, resource allocation, and risk identification as without properly defined tasks, a project is more likely to suffer from miscommunication, accountability issues, and scope creep.

Based on the findings, the study concluded that project task definition has a significant effect on performance of construction projects in North Rift region, Kenya. $\beta_1=0.685$, p value= 0.000). The relationship was considered significant since the p value 0.004 was less than the significant level of 0.05. The study came up with the following recommendations; The management should define project task since it is a critical step in project planning that involves identifying and clearly outlining all the specific actions or units of work necessary to complete a project successfully.

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